

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B212
Date: 14th June 2006
Take Off: 13:33:00
Landing: 16:08:08
Flight Time: 2h35m08

Campaign: CAPEX (AEROPOR & VPRACOP)

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Beja Local Area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Danny Rosenfeld	Hebrew University of Jerusalem
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
7	Cloud Physics	Paul James	Met Office
8	Wet Neph / PSAP	Andy Wilson	Met Office
9	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
10	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
11	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
12	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
13	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office
15	CLAPREC 1	Susana Mendes	University of Evora
16	EUFAAR Training	Piotr Drzewicki	University of Warsaw
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B212 Track 14-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b212
 Date: 14 June 2006
 Project: CAPEX
 Location: Portugal

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
124443		Start-Up	0.70 kft	089	38'05.13N,7'55.65W
131357		event	0.71 kft	116	INU to Nav
132301		Start-Up 4	0.71 kft	116	
132757		start taxi	0.71 kft	116	
133300		T/O	1.6 kft	189	
133553		in cloud	5.7 kft	184	
133602		out cloud	5.9 kft	184	
133723		event	7.0 kft	196	nevzorov zero
133812		event	7.0 kft	199	jw zero
133836		Video start	7.0 kft	199	
134235	134659	Profile 1	7.1 - 3.1 kft	030	
134400		in cloud	5.8 kft	021	
134435		out cloud	5.2 kft	020	
134536		in cloud	4.2 kft	021	
134544		out cloud	4.2 kft	021	
134659	140032	Run 1.1	3.1 kft	088	
140305	140407	Profile 2	3.2 - 4.1 kft	226	
140321		in cloud	3.4 kft	226	
140351		out cloud	3.8 kft	225	
140711	140821	Run 2.1	4.1 kft	100	
140755		in cloud	4.1 kft	105	
140819		out cloud	4.1 kft	098	
141020	141245	Run 3.1	5.0 kft	331	
141048		in cloud	5.0 kft	334	
141122		out cloud	5.0 kft	358	
141131		in cloud	5.0 kft	358	
141141		out cloud	5.0 kft	005	
141203		in cloud	5.0 kft	006	
141216		out cloud	5.0 kft	006	
141231		in cloud	5.0 kft	007	
141443	141650	Run 4.1	6.0 kft	216	
141458		in cloud	6.0 kft	235	
141508		out cloud	6.0 kft	238	
141622		in cloud	6.0 kft	188	
141647		out cloud	6.0 kft	182	
141901	142003	Run 5.1	7.5 kft	044	
141923		in cloud	7.5 kft	076	
142003		out cloud	8.0 kft	032	
142308	142501	Run 6.1	9.0 kft	281	
142401		in cloud	9.0 kft	278	
142448		out cloud	9.0 kft	314	
142756	143226	Run 7.1	10.0 kft	063	
142819		in cloud	10.0 kft	055	
142920		out cloud	10.0 kft	044	
143442	143639	Run 8.1	12.0 kft	321	
143448		in cloud	12.0 kft	321	
143636		out cloud	12.0 kft	327	
144011	144236	Run 9.1	14.0 kft	175	
144048		event	14.0 kft	173	jw zero
144137		in cloud	14.0 kft	166	
144233		out cloud	14.0 kft	166	
144529	144800	Run 10.1	16.0 - 17.9 kft	321	
144529		event			PC crash
145011	145146	Run 11.1	18.2 - 18.0 kft	025	
145027		in cloud	18.1 kft	026	
145052		out cloud	17.9 kft	356	
145102		in cloud	17.9 kft	356	
145112		out cloud	18.0 kft	357	
145121		in cloud	18.0 kft	357	
145144		out cloud	18.0 kft	358	

150735	150953	Run 12.1	20.0 - 19.9 kft	315	
150915		in cloud	20.0 kft	322	
150949		out cloud	20.0 kft	324	
151234	151406	Run 13.1	22.0 kft	175	
151310		in cloud	22.0 kft	175	
151359		out cloud	22.0 kft	174	
151721		event	24.0 kft	009	jw zero
152045	152255	Run 14.1	24.0 - 23.6 kft	049	
152223		in cloud	23.6 kft	044	
152233		out cloud	23.5 kft	043	
152600	152720	Run 15.1	25.0 - 24.9 kft	160	
152650		in cloud	25.0 kft	142	
152717		out cloud	25.0 kft	141	
152755	152854	Run 16.1	23.5 kft	093	
152816		in cloud	23.5 kft	085	
152824		out cloud	23.6 kft	083	
153124	153255	Run 16.2	24.6 - 24.4 kft	299	
153152		in cloud	24.5 kft	307	
153210		out cloud	24.5 kft	311	
153230		in cloud	24.5 kft	333	
153251		out cloud	24.5 kft	359	
153643	153754	Run 17.1	26.0 - 26.1 kft	195	
153707		in cloud	26.0 kft	202	
153722		out cloud	26.1 kft	205	
154619	154828	Run 18.1	28.0 - 27.2 kft	069	
154714		in cloud	28.0 kft	115	
154759		out cloud	28.0 kft	133	
154844		in cloud	26.5 kft	116	
154908		out cloud	25.7 kft	140	
clouds of opportunity					
154959	160808	Profile 3	24.5 - 0.71 kft	201	160808
155503		in cloud	15.5 kft	208	
155525		out cloud	15.2 kft	205	
160151		in cloud	6.1 kft	179	
160208		out cloud	5.8 kft	178	
160243		in cloud	5.0 kft	168	
160304		out cloud	4.7 kft	168	
160808		Land	0.70 kft	164	
161445		Shutdown	0.70 kft	114	38 05.13N 7 55.65W

B212 Track 14-JUN-06

B212 SORTIE BRIEF (Deep convection)

Aerosol Cloud Interaction Sortie (CLAPREC). 14th June 2006

Necessary weather conditions:

Convective clouds over Portugal growing through the 10 kft level.

Trial Objectives:

- To measure vertical profiles of cloud microstructure and precipitation forming processes.
- To document aerosols from natural & anthropogenic sources & relate these to cloud composition and precipitation processes.

Location:

1. Central/S. Portugal
2. Over ocean to the SW of Lisbon

Take Off: 1400L, will be delayed if deep convection is not reported by 1200L

Flight Pattern:

Part 1: Over land

1. Climb northward to 10 kft for identifying the area of cloud activity. (10 minutes)
2. Expedite descend to below cloud base level (estimated 5 kft) and fly to the working area while measuring CCN. (25 minutes)
3. At the work area profile upward through convective clouds. In the case of Cb, concentrate at the upshear feeders. (40 minutes)
4. Terminate upward cloud profile at cloud top level or top of clouds that contain LWC, whatever comes first. Probable highest level in favourable conditions would be 25 kft.

Part 2: Over ocean

We will be able to see potential clouds of interest over the ocean while finishing the cloud profile ascend. If there will be clouds of interest, we will:

1. Fly to an ocean area to the south of Lisbon TMA, doing one CCN spectrum aloft. (10 minutes)
2. After completion of the CCN, expedite to transit air speed, aiming to reach the cloud top altitude over ocean. (20 minutes)
3. Do downward profile through convective clouds. (30 minutes)
4. Do aerosol profile below cloud base descending at 500 fpm, reaching momentarily down to 50 feet. (5 minutes)
5. Do CCN spectrum at 1000 feet while heading home over ocean. Do not cross coastline into land before finishing the CCN spectrum. (10 minutes)
6. Continue towards base alternating between cloud base +1000 feet and cloud base -1000 feet.
7. Landing. (25 minutes).

Total flight time 175 minutes.

Part 2 alternate if there are no suitable clouds over ocean:

1. Fly back to base, while doing CCN spectrum aloft. (10 minutes)
2. Continue descend to base through clouds of opportunity after finishing the CCN spectrum. (25 minutes).

Total flight time 110 minutes.

Research flight: 14 June 2006 Afternoon, CALPREC Portugal

Objectives:

Document convective vertical profiles of aerosols and clouds over land.

Crew aircraft 1:

Pilots:

Flight scientist: Daniel Rosenfeld

Instruments operators:

Synoptic conditions:

The cool air of the upper low now is over Portugal, while the circulation center is still just to the SW of us. An intense squall line passed northward overnight with a spectacular thunder. During morning light showers occurred from moderate depth clouds with tops between 0 and -10C. Cloud base was very low, but rose gradually while breaking the clouds. Deep isolated Cb appeared in the early afternoon, presenting ideal convective towers for our flight. The clouds moved from south to north, with wind of 120/20 kt at takeoff time.

Flight report for Aircraft 1:

We took off as at 13:32 GMT and ascended westward, crossing cloud base at 4600' by 13:35. We continued ascending to 7 kft, where people got into positions, and then descended to 3 kft for CCN measurements at the area S of Beja. The CCN spectrum lasted from 13:46 to 14:00. We started vertical profile of Cu clouds upward, passing through cloud base at 13:42. We kept ascending through the same cloud cluster up to 22 kft. At that height we experienced some instrument problems, (T, DP). We used this for a short crew relief. The instruments became operational again and we continued in the same cloud cluster up to 26 kft. The clouds had ample LWC (up to 1 g m⁻³). Water was observed to run on the aircraft windshield at 26 kft, -33C !

We concentrated on the tops of young growing towers, which glaciated quickly after growing through that level. In order to do that we circled at the area of expected new growth and took the clouds as they were passing through our flight level, with tops visibly growing as we approached them.

At 15:35, 26 kft, we were restricted by ATC and moved to a new cloud cluster about 30 miles to the east, where we penetrated a vigorous tower at the -38C isotherm with 0.1 JW LWC. By this we appear to have documented ample water at -33C and only traces at -38, thereby documenting clouds that freeze their water at the homogeneous freezing level.

After that pass we descended through few clouds of opportunity, documenting well the cloud base and landing at 16:08. Wind at landing was 170/22.

The subsequent passes were:

Time	Height feet	T C	Pass description
14:02	3,400		Ascent 500 fpm through cloud base
14:07	4,000		Return through the same cloud, which was weak
14:10	5,000		Pass at the westward sloping east flanks of a rain cloud.
14:14	6,000		Passing through new towers at the NW side of the shower.
14:18	7,500		Retracing the same cloud. Some rain falling from above.
14:23	9,000		Passing S of the same shower, initially in rain, subsequently in fresh hard not raining cloud.
14:29	10,000	0	Return to the same hard cloud in perpendicular orientation
14:34	12,000		Go to a new cloud to the N, E of a shower. The convective tower was imbedded in a ~1500 feet layer cloud that covered much of the area.
14:36	13,000		Emerging from the top of the layer cloud.
14:41	14,000		Retracing E of the shower in a hard cloud that created a steep wall of cloud above us. Younger cloud elements before exit.
14:46	16,000		Pass S of main shower, initially in glaciated cloud, then in fresh hard tower.
14:49	18,000		Hard isolated tower.
14:51	20,000		Instruments problems. Wait out of clouds. Crew relief. Temperature problem. One thermometer worked, and we resumed working with the same cloud cluster.
15:08	20,000		Moderate tower.
15:12	22,000		Isolated towers that are weakly growing, or sinking. We ran out of growing clouds in the vicinity. The big clouds were glaciating. We flew to a new growing cloud cluster further north.
15:21	23,500		Top of water cloud, sinking.
15:26	25,000		Top of weak water cloud, visibly precipitating below the top.
15:28	23,500		Water cloud, sinking.
15:31	24,500		Two hard towers with graupel.
15:35	26,000		Hard rising tower, 500' below its top. Visible water flowing on the cockpit window. We could not continue in the area due to ATC, so we selected new growing towers to the east.
15:46	28,000		A vigorous strongly growing fresh tower that we intercepted near its top. Sideways there was another higher cloud pushing pileus. We considered this cloud, but at the last minute did not take it because its top was growing too high above us.
15:51	22,000		Abort a penetration to a cloud with top at 28 kft with red echo.
15:54	16,000		The center of an isolated hard tower, without any precipitation.
16:01	6,000		Descending through a medium cumulus.
16:02	4,800		Emerging downward through cloud base.
16:08	600		Landing. Wind 170/22

Impressions

We documented today feeders of Cb that contained ample liquid cloud water up to the homogeneous freezing level. The clouds were not particularly vigorous, and the CCN concentrations were moderate, not exceeding about 1200 cm^{-3} . Highly supercooled liquid water in microphysically continental convective clouds is probably not a rare situation. It was not found yesterday probably due to the strong ice nucleating activity of the desert dust that prevailed at that day, but not today.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:17					wind 150/20 GKH 1010
13:23					ignition
13:32					Takeoff 120/20 wind
13:35		4600			C base
13:36		7000			Level for people getting in
13:42		7000			Decend to 3000' for CCN
13:46		3000			start CCN
14:00		3000			CCN finish go to C base
14:02		3400			C base
14:07		4000			work cloud 0.15
14:10		5000			0.35
14:14		6000			hard
14:15		6000			hard 0.85
14:18		7500			rain from above
14:23		9000			radar hard vertical ridge initially rain upstream
14:27		10000	0°		
14:29					
14:34		12000			
14:36		13000			Engine above 10000
14:41		1410			steep wall left side
14:46		160			partially gl. in 1
14:47		160			second turn or fresh trail
14:49		180			hard is 0.8
		200			instrument problems

Mission Scientist's Log (II) (REV)

(M/Sc 1 - DANNY ROSENFIELD)

Flight No **B.212**.....

Date **14/6/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1333					T/O BETA. R/W 19 3/8-4/8 Cu medicus, little cloud above.
133430					
133630	Climb	6.2kft	155°	37° 45' N 7° 54' W	Temp 7.7°C
133710			→		} Wind 152° / 7m/sec.
133723		Level at FLO70			
134235	P1.	FLO70	031°	37° 36' N 7° 54' W	Start P1 FLO70 ↓ Descend thro clouds as far as possible.
134659	P1ew	3000'	066°	37° 54' N 7° 45' W	End P1 at 3000'; Start CCW SAMPLE.
134659	RUN 1.1 START	3000'			Manoeuvring / ew at 3000' for CCW.
				2-3/8 S/Az	Layer cloud above 4/8 Cu moderate vert develop+ generally
140023	END R1.1	3000'	055°	37° 42' N 7° 54' W	CCW sample finished. END R1
140230					} Searching for suitable area in which to work suitable Cu/CB.
140305	P2 ↑	3000'	226°	37° 36' N 8° 00' W	
140407	P2 INTER.	4.0kft	225°		Interrupt P2 at FLO40.
140711	START R2.1	4.0kft	105°	37° 42' N 8° 06' W	Start Run 2.1
140757					In cloud. (T/W up to 0.15g/m ³)
140823	START R2.1	4.0kft			Out cloud; end run
141020	START R3.1	5.0kft	334°		Start Run 3.1
141052					Into cloud (T/W peak 0.35g/m ³)
141125					Out of cloud
141245		5.0kft			End Run 3.1 at ; turning ↓ thro cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log (2)

 Flight No **B.212**

 Date **14/6/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
141443	START 4.1				Start 4.1
141500	"	5.9kft	→		In cloud. J/W $0.55g/m^3$
141625		-			Into cloud. J/W $0.85g/m^3$
141650	4.1	6.0kft		$37^{\circ} 48' 2''$ $8^{\circ} 6' W$	End R4.1 Climb to FL 075
141901	5.1	7.5kft	061°	$37^{\circ} 48' 2''$ $8^{\circ} 6' W$	Start R5.1
141925		→			Into cloud J/W structure $0.7g/m^3$ Max 8ft/mod turb. here
142003		7.5kft			Out cloud end 5.1
142308	START 6.1	9.0kft	277°		Start R6.1
142402					Into cloud J/W $0.4g/m^3$
142501	END 6.1	9.0kft			End R6.1 Climb to FL 100
142756	START 7.1	10.0kft	054°		Start R7.1
142816			→		Into cloud J/W 2 peaks $0.55g/m^3$ $0.85g/m^3$
143049			→		End Run? Constrained by ATC to be at FL 100 max. Good Cu/ development in area generally layer cloud above (Ac)
143226			→		End R7.1. Climb to FL 120
143442	R 8.1	12.0kft	323°	$38^{\circ} 6' 1''$ $8^{\circ} 12' W$	Start R8.1 (in cloud) J/W $1.05g/m^3$
143639	END 8.1	12.0kft			End R8.1 / Start P. to FL 140 J/W $0.2g/m^3$
144020	START 9.1	14.0kft	172°		Start R9.1 J/W peak $0.7g/m^3$
144135					Into cloud 4000, some ice detected (flight deck)

J/W 2000 $0.1g/m^3$ ↓
[between 28.1 & 29.1]

Mission Scientist's Log (2)

 Flight No **B.212**.....

 Date **14/6/06**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144236	9.1	FL140			End R 9.1 at FL140. Climb to FL160.
144529	10.1	FL160	267°	38° 6' W 8° 12' W	Start R 10.1
144705		→			Enter cloud now. <u>J/W 0.85 g/m³ Max</u>
144800		FL160			End R 10.1. [STILL WELL ZEROED]
					Climb to FL180.
145014	11.1	FL180	026°		Start R 11.1
145038		←			Enter cloud now. <u>J/W 1.0 g/m³</u>
145050					Out cloud.
145140		FL180			End R 11.1 Climb FL 200
					Some instrument problems (DI Temp fallen over - gone to FULL SCALE). NDI Temp OK
1459		→			← NDI Temp & Dew Pt now gone too CCN sample to be taken whilst manoeuvring to try & regain DI Temp sensor.
150450		→			CCN sample taking long time at this ht. NDI Temp / Dew Pt now back OK.
					Will proceed to start further Cu penetration see
150735	12.1	FL200	314°	38° 6' W 8° 10' W	Start R 12.1 WIND 142° / 38 kts
150920					Into cloud now <u>J/W 0.8 g/m³</u>
1510		→			End R 12.1. Climb to FL 220
151225	13.1	FL220	175°		Start R 13.1
151316					Into cloud <u>J/W 0.15 g/m³</u>
151406		FL220			Out of cloud & end Run 13.1 [Mostly ice x/ks not]
151730		←			Manoeuvring to find another good Cu to next [DI TEMP BACK].

Mission Scientist's Log (2)

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1517		→			J/W 20000 now.
152045	^R 14.1	FL240	045°	38° 30' N 5° 12' W	Start Run 14.1 at FL240
		↓ ←			dropping to FL235 to penetrate Cu top
152215			→		Into cloud (J/W 0.1 g/m ³)
152255	^R 14.1	FL240			End Run 14.1
152600	15.1	FL250 (35.0kft)	141°	38° 36' N 5° 15' W	Start Run 15.1
152650					Into cloud (v. top of Cu)
152702					Out cloud, end run.
					Descend to catch to FL235
152755					Start Run 16.1
152813		FL235			Enter cloud. (J/W 0.7 g/m ³)
152820					Out of cloud. / end Run 16.1
152854		FL235			←
153110					Climb to FL245.
153124					Start Run 16.2
~ 153150		FL245			Into cloud → (J/W 0.7 g/m ³)
153205					Out of cloud
153240		FL245			Into cloud (J/W 0.7 g/m ³)
153251					Out of cloud
153255					End Run 16.2 [D.I. Temp now u/s again]
1536.					NEVZLOV VANE SKEN ?
153643		FL260			Run 17.1 → NEW LWC NEW TOTAL WC
153705					In cloud (J/W 0.35 g/m ³)
153720					Out of cloud
153754		FL260			End Run 17.1 Climb to FL280.

154055

←

D.I. Temp OK now

 X
NOT
OK.

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Date 14/6/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
154618		FL280			Start R18 J/W 0.4 g/m³
154713					into cloud
154828		FL280			End R18.1
					Descending all way down thro' clouds of opportunity towards BEJA & prepare to land.
154959	P3	FL280 →			Start P3 ↓
					^{1/8} - 6/8 Cu/Cb with owl Ae layers (Tops to FL300)
155408		15.5kt			} into cloud (last time) (J/W 1.4 g/m ³ LARGEST! TERRA)
15					
155925			←		Return to BEJA to land [DI Temp fallen over again]
160220		5600'		-	Out of cloud J/W 0.35 g/m³
160247					into cloud
160305		4700-4800'			Out cloud & descend to land now (C. base locally).
1608	LAND				
1333	T/O				
2:35	h h				

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B212

Date : 14/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

No time to carry out zeros on NO_x or Ozone instruments before security for flight B11 (on the same day).

CO	Background ppbV became very high above FL150, resulting in unreliable data, especially during profile descent after calibration.
O₃	None
NO_x	No flow through Ozonator at FL150 and above therefore only NO channel available (no NO₂ or NO_x measurements). Flow did not recover on descent until FL100.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

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①B

FLIGHT NUMBER: B DATE: 14/06/06 OPERATOR: B.G.D Page 1 of 2
 PROJECT: CAPEX

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		14000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Height?
1347:35	1348:50	26.23	23.97	0.17	0.31	0.48	0.70	1.06	S Run 1-1
		26.32	23.29	475	560	1149	1306	1975	D
		26.29	22.52	451	496	489	622	883	B Note 'B' value rises 0.4 & 0.5
		26.32	21.78	2348	2267	2310	2140	2153	R
err @		26.22	20.69	989.4	989.5	989.3	989.4	989.4	P
14:00:10		15000'							'B' trimmer adj.
Stop @		26.27	23.28	0.17	0.30	0.49	0.70	1.05	S 1st sample
14:02:12	21:12	26.31	23.28	685	1069	845	1303	1435	D retained
		26.23	22.5	584	512	453	419	521	B & analysed on climb
err @		26.22	21.71	2148	2152	2164	2164	2171	R to Run 2-1
14:11:02	20:02	26.20	20.71	989.4	989.4	992.9	992.8	992.9	P (& during Run 2-1)
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
1459:16	1459:59	26.28	23.60	0.17	0.32				S Sample
		26.00	22.47	187					D retained
				197					B for analysis when level
				2333					R
				908.5					P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

213 212

2B

FLIGHT NUMBER: B DATE: 14/06/06 OPERATOR: B. GIDDINGS Page 1 of 2
 PROJECT:

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
		25000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
15:23:00		25.59	23.16	0.17	0.32	0.49	0.72	1.07	S	Previous sample
		25.16	22.13	281	358	595	1162	1256	D	analysed
Not B value		25.12	21.31	386	493	575	554	563	B	@ FL 250
q P value		25.25	20.51	2367	2363	2361	2359	2360	R	@ time 235
with change in weight		25.12	19.48	866.1	857.6	884	870.8	870.3	P	15:23:00
									S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	
									S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B211

Location: Baja, Panama

page 2 of

Date: 11/16/06

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution: 2

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
105328	B2-1	B211T	clsd	71.0	31.1	17.6	-190.6	21.7	CH1 x 2.	
105446	B3-1	B211U	open	70.4	30.9	18.0	-190.6	22.1	Z1 x 8	ISO 5710
105858	B3-1	B211V	clsd	71.1	31.4	21.3	-190.6	22.9	Z1 x 2	
105957	" "	B211W	open	70.2	31.0	21.0	-190.6	23.0	Z1 x 2	
110109	" "	B211X	clsd	71.1	31.0	21.6	-190.6	23.3	CH1 x 2	
110224	" "	B211Y	open						Z1 x 8.	
110619	" "	B211Z	clsd	71.2	32.1	23.3	-190.6		N1 x 2	
110730	" "	B211φ	open						Z1 x 2	
110845	" "	B2111	clsd	71.3	31.9	23.8	-190.6	24.5	CH1 x 2	
110902	" "	B2112	open			23.8	-190.6	24.6	Z1 x 8	
111357	" "	B2113	clsd	71.1	33.2	24.8	-190.6	25.3	N1 x 2	
111512	" "	B2114	open						Z1 x 2.	
111624	" "	B2115	clsd	71.0	33.5	25.1	-190.6	25.6	CH1 x 2.	
111737	" "	B2116	open			25.4	-190.6	25.8	Z1 x 8	
112139	" "	B2117	clsd	71.2	34.7	25.4	-190.6	25.6	N1 x 2	
112258	" "	B2118	open						Z1 x 2	shutter closed at start
112409	" "	B2119	open						Z1 x 2	
112511	end B3-1	B211A	clsd	71.0	35.2	25.1	-190.6	26.2	CH1 x 2	

1125

ARIES flight log

Flight: B211

Location: Baja, Panama

page 3 of

Date: 11/6/01

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes: RAPEX

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
112935	R4-1	C211B	Clso	71.0	33.6	24.9	-190.6	24.7	CHx2	
113740	R4-1	C211C	Clso	70.9	31.4	22.6	-189.9	27.3	CHx2 CHx2	
113849	R4-1	C211D	Clso						N1x8	
114254	R4-1	C211E	open						Z1x2	
114408	R4-1	C211F	Clso	71.0	31.0	17.8	-190.6		CHx2 N1x2	
114519	R4-1	C211G	Clso	70.9	30.8	17.8	-190.6	25.4	CHx2	
114631	R4-1	C211H	Clso						N1x8	
115037	R4-1	C211I	Clso open						Z1x2	
115156	R4-1	C211J	Clso			15.8	-190.6	23.9	N1x2	
115310	R4-1	C211K	Clso	70.9	30.8	16.0	-190.6	24.4	CHx2	
115425	R4-1	C211L	Clso	70.9	30.8	16.0	-190.6	24.9	N1x8	
115833	R4-1	C211M	open	70.5	30.8	15.1	-190.6	24.1	Z1x2 Z1x3	
120016	R4-1	C211N	Clso	71.0	30.9	14.6	-190.6	23.5	CH	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	14/6/06	Flight	B212	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAPEX			
Departure	Beja	Arrival	Beja			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					12:50
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	54°C	Ch	58°C	Ch18	40°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot	340.0	Cold	301.2		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not fitted					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud	7/8 mixed level	Precip	No		
	Surface	Dry	Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot				Cold
	Deimos:	Hot				Cold
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.212**.....

 Date 14/06/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 1 of 3.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
133351								T/O from Beja
134220	✓	070	11.9	38 *	78 *	-	41c	data record start
134235	P1	070 ↓	12.4	35.45 *	79.8 *	-	41c	start P1
134659	P1	300ft	13.2	38.58 *	83 *			Dry Neph RH suspect!! using average of RH1 & RH3 for dry neph RH figure. RH5 (after humidifier) and RH6 (wet neph) shows good agreement.
134833	R1.1	300ft	13.0	36	84	-	41c	start R1.1 - Growing Cumulus cloud penetrations.
140032	R1.1	"	13.0	38	86		41c	end R1.1
140711	R2.1	400ft	12.6	34	87.6	-	41	start R2.1
140821	"	"	"	"	"	"	"	end R2.1
141020	R3.1	500ft	12.4	33	86.8		41c	start R3.1
141245	R3.1	"	11.9	"	"	"	"	end R3.1
141443	R4.1	FLO60	11.9	28	87	-	41c	start R4.1
141650	"	"	11.9	28	87	-	41c	end R4.1
141901	R5.1	FLO75	11.4	27	88	-	41c	start R5.1 bumpy!
142003	"	"	11.4	26	88	-	41c	end R5.1
142308	R6.1	FLO90	10.8	22	88	-	41c	start R6.1
142501	R6.1	"	"	21	88	"	"	end R6.1
142756	R7.1	8100	10.5	20	88.5	"	"	start R7.1
143226	"	"	10.4	18	89.7	"	"	end R7.1

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B** 212

Date 14/06/06

Operator's name: Wilson

Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
143442	R8.1	FL120	10.9	18	89	-	41	Start R8.1 - in Cloud - bumpy!
143639	-"-	-"-	10.9	18	89	-	41c	end R8.1
144011	R9.1	FL140	10.9	13	88	-	41c	Start R9.1, RH1, Dry Neph RH & RH3 all in agreement now!
144236	R9.1	FL140	10.9	13	88	-	41c	end R9.1
144629	R10.1	FL160	10.1	9	89	-	41c	Start R10.1
144708	R10.1	-"-	10.0	11	89	-"	-"-	in cloud.
144800	R10.1	-"-	10.0	10	89	-"	-"-	end R10.1 Dry Neph RH now less than RH1 & RH3
145011	R11.1	FL180	11.4	7	86	-"-	-"-	Start R11.1
145036	-"-	FL180	11.5	8	86	-"	-"-	in cloud
145146	-"-	-"-	11.5	8	86	-"-	41c	end R11.1.
150735	R12.1	FL200	10.6	3.7	87.6	-"-	41c	Start R12.1
150920	-"-	-"-	10.6	5	88	-"	-"-	in cloud
150953	R12.1	FL200	10.7	4	87.6	-"-	41c	end R12.1
151234	R13.1	FL220	10.6	3	86.8	-"-	41c	Start R13.1
151406	-"	-"-	10.6	3	87.6	-"	41c	end R13.1, Quite bumpy through the cloud.
152045	R14.1	FL240	11.2	3	87.6	-"	41c	Start R14.1.
152130	-"-	FL235	11.3	3	86.8	-"	-"-	dropping soft to be in cloud
152230	-"-	FL235	11.3	3.6	87	-"-	41c	in cloud
152255	R14.1	-"-	11.4	3.7	87	-"	41c	end R14.1
152600	R15.1	FL250	10.9	3	88	-	41	Start R15.1 through very top of cloud.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B212	Date	14/06/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	1
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

1240						Laptop time set			
						Sws video u/s, sws and shims not cleaned due to security issues...			
133258						T/o Beja			
1341			shims	50	200	Shims ok		x	
1341			Zen + 6	30	200	Sws ok	x		
134235	P1	FL70				Start profile			
134659	R1	3000'	Zen + 6	30	200	End profile, start run, cloud above	x		
140032						End run			
140305	P2	3000'	Zen + 6	30	200	Start profile			
140407		FL040				End profile			
140711	R2	4000'	Zen + 6	30	200	Start run			
140821						End run			
141020	R3	5000'	Zen + 6	50	200	Start run, sws vis module dropped out			
141245						End run			
141443	R4	FL60	Zen + 6	50	200	Start run, sws vis still u/s			
141615 ?						End run			
141902	R5	FL75	Zen + 6	50	200	Start run, vis module back			
142003						End run			
142308	R6	FL90	"	"	"	Start run			
142501						End run			
142758	R7	FL100	"	"	"	Start run			
143226						End run			
143442	R8	FL120	"	"	"	Start run			
143634						End run			
144014	R9	FL140	"	"	"	Start run, some cloud above			
144235						End run			
144612	R10	FL160	"	"	"	Start run			
144758						End run			
145012	R11	FL180	"	"	"	Start run, Ci above			
145148						End run			
150732	R12	FL200	"	"	"	Start run			
150954						End run			
151234	R13	FL220	"	"	"	Start run, unsure if cloud above or not			
151406						End run			
152046	R14	FL235	"	"	"	Start run, some Ci above...?			
152256						End run			
152604	R15	FL250	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, broken cloud below, patchy Ci above			
152720						End run			
152758	R16	FL235	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, patchy Ci above			
152854						End run			
1531?	R16.2?	FL245	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, thin Ci above?			
153300						End run			
153630	R17	FL260	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, patchy Ci above			
153755						End run			
154619	R18	FL280	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, patchy Ci around			

BEJA,

AFWA MM5 Output 1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC) ->	986	687	170	11
	975	1018	175	18
	950	1748	175	22
	925	2494	175	23
	900	3252	180	23
	875	4030	180	24
	850	4824	185	23
	800	6467	185	24
	750	8198	170	28
	700	10035	165	30
	650	11988	170	30
	600	14088	170	33
	550	16295	175	37
	500	18693	175	41
	450	21283	170	44
	400	24098	170	46
	350	27201	170	45
	300	30671	170	44
	250	34653	170	45
	200	39441	170	41
	150	45585	180	24
	100	54130	170	23

Lid Strength Index = -0.396634
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5607m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1379m
 SWEAT = 203
 Environ. Helicity = -32
 Storm Rel. Helicity = 35

CAPE = 463
 K Index = 22
 Total Totals = 47
 Lifted Index = -0
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UWV = 0.0323219 at 700mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 67%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.68C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.21C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 6.98C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 1.09in

036 HR FCST SKEW-T
 12Z 14-JUN-2006

LCL

GRID PNT LAT = 38.15 LON = -7.68
 STATION LAT = 38.016 LON = -7.866

BEJA,

AFWA MM5 Output

1 1.5

	Pressure	Height	W Dir	W Speed
(SPC) ->	986	687	145	8
	975	1008	155	18
	950	1737	160	23
	925	2481	165	24
	900	3242	170	24
	875	4019	175	24
	850	4814	180	23
	800	6461	180	22
	750	8196	180	23
	700	10029	175	27
	650	11982	175	32
	600	14061	180	36
	550	16285	180	37
	500	18675	185	40
	450	21257	185	43
	400	24065	185	44
	350	27187	185	43
	300	30640	185	41
	250	34625	185	38
	200	39412	185	34
	150	45558	180	26
	100	54120	180	23

Lid Strength Index = -0.740099
 Thickness 1000mb - 500mb = 5604m
 Thickness 1000mb - 850mb = 1376m
 SWEAT = 210
 Environ. Helicity = 59
 Storm Rel. Helicity = 91

CAPE = 694
 K Index = 30
 Total Totale = 49
 Lifted Index = -1
 Convective Inhibition = 0
 Max UVV = 0.0350342 at 250mb
 Mean Rel Humid 1000-500mb = 75%
 Lapse Rate 850mb - 500mb = 5.96C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 500mb = 6.22C/Km
 Lapse Rate 700mb - 400mb = 6.86C/Km
 Precipitable Water = 1.2In

042 HR FCST SKEW-T
 18Z 14-JUN-2006

LCL

GRID PNT LAT = 38.15 LON = -7.68
 STATION LAT = 38.016 LON = -7.866

AFWA NW-SE MM5 45Km
 RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C)
 VALID:12Z14JUN2006

Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.

NW

SE

AFWA NW-SE MM5 45Km
 RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C)
 VALID:18Z14JUN2006

NW **Note:** Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight. SE